

Article

Adaptation of Augmentative and Alternative Communicators through the Study of Interactions with High-Tech Solution Users

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Abstract: Augmentative and Alternative Communication (AAC) strategies ease communication tasks for people who require accessible solutions. These strategies are usually addressed by technological solutions such as mobile applications. This research seeks clues on the development of such applications by analyzing user interactions with Android application PictoDroid Lite, an AAC communicator. This study considered a data set containing more than 85,000 interactions of users from more than 50 countries. The goal was to identify the primary needs reflected in the users' behavior and how these applications handle them, providing other researchers and developers with relevant information about how users interact with these applications. We detected areas of improvement regarding the adaptation to users' needs in terms of profiling, smart suggestions, and time habits.

Keywords: augmentative and alternative communication; pictogram; mobile application; user interaction; sentiment analysis; large language models

Citation: González-González, J.; Costa-Montenegro, E.; García-Doval, F.M.; López-Bravo, C.; de Arriba-Pérez, F. Adaptation of Augmentative and Alternative Communicators through the Study of Interactions with High-Tech Solution Users. *Appl. Sci.* **2024**, *14*, 5641. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app14135641>

Academic Editor: Juan Francisco De Paz Santana

Received: 20 May 2024

Revised: 21 June 2024

Accepted: 25 June 2024

Published: 28 June 2024

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1. Introduction

Augmentative and alternative communication (AAC) is a discipline that “studies and, when necessary, compensates for temporary or permanent impairments, activity limitations, and participation restrictions of persons with severe disorders of speech-language production and/or comprehension, including spoken and written modes of communication” [1]. Within the field of AAC, there exist multiple strategies to ease accessibility for those who need it.

One of the multiple solutions proposed to date is the use of specific software that assists in user communication [2]. In this context, in 2011, our research team published Android application PictoDroid Lite. It enables users to communicate using pictograms or images with their corresponding descriptions. The combination of multiple pictograms allows for the creation of different types of sentences. As we discuss later in this research, this solution is widely accepted and easily comparable with many other available applications.

The application offers two different modes of verbal expression. Punctual mode presents a group of indexed pictograms for easy, straightforward communication using simple sentences. Alternatively, the cumulative mode offers an evolved system of phrasal construction where users autonomously pick any pictograms needed to convey different pieces of information adapted to their communicative needs by means of more complex sentences.

We decided to carry out a wide-ranging exploratory analysis, studying interactions from hundreds of users representing a larger number of participants than the average for similar studies [3]. Unlike cited research, our study focuses on analyzing usage patterns from interactions of real users with communication impairments. This perspective

differs from studies that directly evaluate user experiences via questionnaires, a matter which has already been proven positive for similar applications [4–6]. However, we value the significance of the user experience, as our particular app is endorsed by more than 50,000 downloads and plenty of positive feedback from users.

This novel study of usage patterns offers hints on how to best adapt applications to the needs of end users who require accessible solutions in their daily interactions by using data analysis and Artificial Intelligence (AI).

Therefore, the main objective of this research is to shed light on everyday habits of AAC application users by studying how they interact with a high-tech AAC solution. This can provide insights into how to offer better tailoring to their daily needs and a better and more profound comprehension of the intentions and purposes they attach to these applications. With these hints, we expect not only to foster the use of these AAC solutions but also to offer a better user experience. This will inform future developments in this area.

When reviewing previous works on AAC strategies, relevant research highlights that it is possible to classify them according to the following three main characteristics: purpose, autonomy, and use of technology [7]. We drafted this analysis of related works using a hierarchical vision to contextualize the application design that led to our study.

The purpose of AAC strategies depends on their desired effect on the preserved abilities of the user. Taking that into account, we can distinguish between rehabilitation and habilitation as follows:

- Rehabilitating solutions help users in the recovery of their communication capabilities [8,9].
- Habilitating solutions assist users in acquiring new communicative competencies [10].

Regarding autonomy, the literature defines a classification regarding the involvement of external assistance in AAC strategies. Figure 1 contains a graphic explaining the complete hierarchy of solutions in terms of autonomy. Thus, the more abstract levels that group them are unaided and aided solutions:

Figure 1. Hierarchy of AAC solutions.

- Unaided solutions include a wide variety of techniques that only depend on the user [11,12]. They usually involve symbols, sign language [13], or Enhanced Natural Gestures (ENG) [14].
- Aided solutions are strategies that require external devices or assistance during the communication process [3,15]. These solutions can be classified into low-technology and high-technology approaches.
 - Low-tech solutions include non-electronic strategies such as the Picture Exchange Communication System (PECS) [16] or alphabet and symbol boards [17,18].
 - High-tech solutions refer to any computer-based strategy [2,19], including mobile applications [20–23], artificial intelligence applications [24], and other technologies, for example, augmented reality [25].

Finally, it is important to add that high-tech solutions present multiple means of interaction depending on the patient's needs [26].

- Eye tracking: Scanning of eye movements and their position relative to a digital display [27,28].
- Touch displays: This is the most used input method nowadays. It requires the user to interact physically with a touch screen [20–23].
- Muscular activity recognition: Specific devices that capture voluntary or involuntary body actions. This can be achieved in the following different ways:
 - Mechanical activation: Detection of physical movements or gestures [29,30];
 - Respiratory activation: Detection of respiratory signals [31].
- Brain–computer interfaces: Scanning and modulation of electric brain signals [32].

PictoDroid Lite is an aided, high-tech solution. Although it can be used as a rehabilitating resource, its use is predominantly habilitating new communicative competencies. The application presents the user with a grid of pictograms to select from a touch screen. Pictogram communicators have been widely used and consistently proven useful in the literature [4–6]. It is important to point out that no dedicated device or specific training is required, and any Android mobile device will run the application effectively. Table 1 shows applications with methods similar to PictoDroid Lite.

Table 1. Android applications similar to PictoDroid Lite.

Application	Type	Graphics	Released on	Downloads
JABtalk ¹	Communicator	Others	October 2011	+100,000
PictoDroid Lite ²	Communicator	Pictogram + Others	November 2011	+50,000
Dictapicto ³	Translator	Pictogram	December 2016	+100,000
Card Talk ⁴	Communicator	Pictogram + Others	April 2017	+100,000
SymboTalk ⁵	Communicator	Pictogram + Others	January 2018	+100,000
Twinkl Symbols ⁶	Communicator	Pictogram + Others	January 2021	+10,000
Click AAC ⁷	Translator	Pictogram	June 2021	+5000
Search of Arasaac ⁸	Translator	Pictogram	December 2021	+50,000

¹ Available at <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.jabstone.jabtalk.basic>, 24 June 2024; ² Available at <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.uvigo.gti.PictoDroidLite>, 24 June 2024; ³ Available at <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.orange.dictapicto>, 24 June 2024; ⁴ Available at <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=jp.co.litalico.cardtalk>, 24 June 2024; ⁵ Available at <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.elelad.comboard>, 24 June 2024; ⁶ Available at <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=co.uk.twinkl.symbolwriter>, 24 June 2024; ⁷ Available at <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.clickAAC>, 24 June 2024; ⁸ Available at <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=it.alessandrolarocca.searchonarasaac>, 24 June 2024.

Communicators allow users to express themselves, while translators define a set of images or pictograms corresponding to an existing natural language expression. Applications typically use pictograms as their basic graphical representations, and many of them permit the use of external sources such as photographs or drawings.

After confirming it as a popular technological solution for AAC, the research team decided to conduct this study to offer relevant information for other researchers developing similar solutions. Any fully developed application has the potential for improvement, benefiting from the knowledge provided in this study.

Regarding previous research, we consider that this research cannot be compared qualitatively to others available in the literature. Many previous studies focus either on assessing usage experience by asking participants to fill out a questionnaire or evaluating their performance according to predefined metrics [5,33–35]. Nonetheless, this study observes how these users interact with the proposed AAC solution.

Our study implements a different approach, exploring usage patterns gathered from a larger audience with no need for additional interviews. With this technological perspective, we aim to analyze the possibilities of state-of-the-art AAC technologies to adapt to users' needs, preferences, and habits. The conclusions drawn from this paper could potentially encourage developers and researchers to undertake fundamental upgrades to their high-tech solutions, leading to a better AAC user experience.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 details the design and operation of PictoDroid Lite. Section 3 introduces the method of our study and the final data set and specifies how data were collected. Section 4 presents the conducted tests and their results. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper and presents directions for future work in this field.

2. Materials

The main objective of this study is to offer an analysis of the most prevalent uses of an AAC application intended to facilitate communication through pictograms. PictoDroid Lite is a free Android application that allows users to communicate through pictograms or pictures and their corresponding text. The app has reached more than 50,000 downloads in more than 50 countries, predominantly in Spanish-speaking countries. In order to fully comprehend the data gathered for this project, we consider it necessary to briefly explain the main characteristics of the software that captured the interactions.

2.1. Functionality

PictoDroid Lite presents the user with a grid of different elements used to communicate in familiar environments. Each element includes a pictogram (or any other visual representation of a linguistic meaning) and its corresponding written text. The app also includes an oral form that can be identical to or different from the written text. This oral form might be played by a media player (when an audio file is included) or generated by the device's voice synthesizer. This functionality is comparable to other AAC applications listed in Table 1. There is also a resemblance with other low-tech solutions, such as symbol boards.

The pictograms can represent a semantic field or some other linguistic category (for example, food) or stand only for themselves (for example, apple). In the former case, selecting a pictogram implies accessing that category (a sublevel with similar display and distribution) to complete the message. This is what we refer to as pictogram indexation. With respect to the latter, the selection of a pictogram terminates the sentence itself. A final pictogram concludes the utterance, and when selected, the application automatically returns to the initial main screen after a few seconds.

The application has two modes of communication, namely punctual or cumulative communication, aimed clearly towards communication or language acquisition and development, respectively. These options are vital for the user's learning process, as they allow them to adjust the communication board to their cognitive, developmental, and social abilities at that time. They range from fewer to more pictograms on the screen, thus

avoiding distraction or confusion with unnecessary ones. Punctual mode (see Figure 2) is intended for immediate, straightforward interaction. Cumulative mode (see Figure 3) presents a more complex functioning where the user must select the different pieces of information that form the final sentence before the voice synthesizer expresses it. Additionally, the cumulative mode may apply a layer of Natural Language Generation (NLG) that is currently only available for the Spanish language, which applies verb conjugations, as well as the introduction of determiners and connectors García-Méndez et al. [36]. This NLG layer provides the user with a socially appropriate utterance and a valid sentence model. As far as we know, no other AAC communicator includes an NLG layer in Spanish.

Figure 2. Punctual screen mode.

Figure 3. Cumulative screen mode.

2.2. Configuration

As previously stated, this app is fully configurable to meet each user's needs. Regarding verbal communication, the app is available in six languages (Spanish, French, Italian, German, English, and Swedish). The user can independently choose the language of the application and the language of the voice synthesizer, allowing for multilingual communication. As additional options, the user (or an assistant) may choose if the voice synthesizer is enabled; the modes previously presented; and, for the latter, the application of the NLG adaptation layer. Furthermore, the user can decide about the dimensions of the image grid presented on the different screens (to better adapt to their visual capabilities or preferences), among many other visual options.

Regarding pictogram administration, the application offers a manager that allows the user (or an assistant) to create new pictograms and categories; change meanings and representations; and modify the oral expressions, including recording voices and sounds, etc. All these features meet the vocabulary configuration need highlighted in previous research Caron et al. [37]. New pictograms or images can be registered using the device camera, loading an image from the gallery, or downloading a standardized pictogram from the ARASAAC repository (available at <https://arasaac.org/pictograms/search>, 24 June 2024).

Finally, the application includes a profile manager feature, which makes it possible to create, import, and export multiple profiles. This feature allows different people to use a single device still adapted to their specific needs. However, it also facilitates a single user in maintaining different profiles adapted to different contexts (e.g., family, school, or health care). By default, the application offers a basic profile for both modes (punctual and cumulative), including two additional profiles with masculine or feminine pronouns, a very relevant feature in languages with solid gender marks, such as Spanish or French.

3. Methodology and Implementation

This section presents the design of the study and the final data set for the research, along with the implementations that were necessary to carry it out.

3.1. Research Design

Figure 4 presents a general view of the research structure. The study's methodology is defined as follows.

Figure 4. Architecture of the study.

The general architecture of the experiment consists of three parts, namely the use of an external platform for data collection, a preprocessing module, and an exploratory module. The final output of the research is a report containing all the insights studied later.

3.1.1. Data Collection

Our application is configured to collect anonymized usage data automatically. This data collection occurs each time a user performs any of the selected actions, namely (i) generation of sentences and (ii) creation, edition, or deletion of pictograms/images. For this purpose, it was necessary to establish a cloud storage system to collect this information in real time. In order to respect users' privacy, no personal data are collected, and all registered events are automatically anonymized.

Each user who generates at least one event with the application has a record in the database, with a unique identifier present in every registered action. The identifier, provided by the Android API, does not have any relation to the real information of the user, so no personal data are compromised. Additionally, we track the profile names registered by the application in order to sort different users. This allows us to distinguish between different people using the same device. Nonetheless, this field is equivalent to an identifier, and it is not used for the analysis. This record also contains the country from which such events are generated for statistical purposes. Depending on the type of action executed, the application provides different values. Every action is accompanied by its timestamp referencing local time.

For generation events, the app registers the final sentence, the mode of generation (punctual or cumulative) that was used, the language or languages chosen for the application, and the voice synthesizer (as they might be different). For the cumulative mode, the app registers the final sentence after the NLG phase, if available. For new pictograms or images, it records the item's name, the source of the image that represents it, the application's language and mode, and the categories to which the new picture belongs, if applicable. The latter also applies to deletion events, ignoring the source of the original image. Finally, the app registers the update of those elements whenever they change the associated written or oral text, as this is the meaningful part of the communication feature.

3.1.2. Preprocessing Module

First, data are retrieved from the cloud database and presented in a format suitable for processing. The data are divided into sets according to their nature, namely users, generation, new pictograms, updated pictograms, and deleted pictograms. The user table includes information related to the origin and the number of interactions from each type that the user has generated. The remaining tables include the data described in the previous subsection, adding the corresponding user identifier to each entry to guarantee its traceability.

For this research, only Spanish-speaking users are considered in the analysis, so the tables are filtered by language. We made this decision as Spanish is the only language represented in the data set with enough samples to conduct an exhaustive study (see Table 2). Free text fields (generated sentences, pictogram names, etc.) undergo minor modifications, like letter case change or graphic accent removal, to maximize coincidences. Major modifications such as lemmatization or stop-word removal are counterproductive, as the phrases' length and complexity are relevant to this research.

Table 2. Global and Spanish distribution of samples by event type.

Entry Type		Global	Spanish
Sentence generations	Punctual	79,793	72,308
	Cumulative	887	801
New pictograms	Punctual	2180	2096
	Cumulative	435	435
Deleted pictograms	Punctual	1939	1922
	Cumulative	157	157
Updated pictograms	Punctual	610	595
	Cumulative	20	20

Each entry is associated with a predefined category according to its meaning. The categorization requires manually labeled phrases in order to ensure consistency.

3.1.3. Exploratory Module

This research aims to extract relevant conclusions from the usage habits of an AAC application. When determining which tests to perform with the data, it is essential to keep in mind the depth and format of the data. Thus, the tests must be defined based on the preliminary observations made by the research team.

The tests are divided according to the type of event being analyzed (text generation or creation of new pictograms). Expert personnel should determine which are the most relevant aspects of the data to proceed with an exploratory analysis. A subsection of experiments involves sentiment analysis (SA) of the generated texts and the pictograms added by users in order to understand the main motivations for using the application.

3.2. Dataset Description

The data set contains 85,165 different entries in five languages (Spanish, French, English, Italian, and German, in descending order of prevalence). The data set contains the interactions generated by 2370 users from more than 50 different countries in the period between 18 November 2022 and 10 July 2023. Table 2 shows the distribution of entries by type of event. Table 3 presents the most represented countries in the data set.

Table 3. Eight most represented countries in the data set by number of entries.

Country	Users	Entries
Spain	38.80%	63.61%
Argentina	12.28%	7.46%
Chile	8.33%	5.51%
France	1.91%	4.57%
Mexico	7.69%	4.21%
Ecuador	2.34%	3.64%
Colombia	3.70%	2.13%
Peru	4.72%	1.11%

The predominant use of the application by Spanish-speaking users led to the decision to focus this research on the Spanish interactions of 1875 users. Additionally, we limited the scope of the study to interactions and pictograms generated with the punctual mode of the application, since the cumulative mode represent less than 2% of all the interactions. The highly adaptable nature of this mode adds an overwhelming amount of variability and makes it unsuitable for the methods and scope of this study. At this point, it is important to highlight the potential of these types of applications to reach Low- and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs) [38].

Regarding the accessibility of the devices used to run PictoDroid Lite, we studied the different formats of hardware used, as they condition how the screen is displayed. We know that 77% of users work with tablet devices, benefiting from larger displays that ease navigation through the pictogram grids, whereas 14% of the users work with smartphones, leaving the remaining 9% to unknown sources (devices that are not identified by Google).

3.3. Dataset Structure

Depending on the type of event, the number and type of retrieved parameters differ. The following subsection describes each set of data and their characteristics. Tables 4–7 present examples of the fields retrieved for each type of event contained in the data set.

All the events share a common group of parameters (index, user, event, mode, and language) that identify the entries, the user who generated them, the app mode used, and the language they are written in. Additionally, each event has some of the following particular fields adapted to its characteristics:

- Generation: The language synthesizer field contains the language of the text-to-speech tool used to pronounce the generated phrase . The **phrase** field contains the generated phrase.
- New and deleted pictograms: The **name** field contains the name of the new pictogram. The **category** field includes the indexation of the particular pictogram. For new pictograms, the **source** field contains the origin of the image used to represent it.
- Updated pictograms: The **old name** and **old voice** field represent the name and voice (the text read by the text-to-speech tool) that are being substituted, respectively, and the **new name** and **new voice** fields the new versions of them. As in new and deleted pictograms, the **category** field contains the indexation of the updated pictogram.

Table 4. Generation entry examples.

Index	User	Event	Language	Language Synth.	Mode	Phrase	Timestamp
1066	9	Generation	Español	es	PUNCTUAL	quiero leer una revista	2023-04-22 18:04:51.805
3976	105	Generation	Español	es	PUNCTUAL	me duele la garganta	2022-12-20 10:51:47.604
4235	115	Generation	Español	es	PUNCTUAL	quiero beber zumo	2023-04-08 08:47:25.255

Table 5. New pictogram entry examples.

Index	User	Event	Language	Mode	Name	Source	Timestamp	Category
1797	1335	NewPicto	Español	PUNCTUAL	galletas	ARASAAC	2023-07-05 10:10:07.12	[Comer]
1832	1475	NewPicto	Español	PUNCTUAL	futbol	PHOTO	2023-05-22 17:27:05.993	[deportes]
1891	1683	NewPicto	Español	PUNCTUAL	Calmado	GALLERY	2023-04-18 15:01:33.666	[Emociones]

Table 6. Deleted pictogram entry examples.

Index	User	Event	Language	Mode	Name	Timestamp	Category
68	11	DeletePicto	Español	PUNCTUAL	coca-cola	2023-05-02 18:45:20.317	[quiero beber]
402	142	DeletePicto	Español	PUNCTUAL	echar colonia	2023-02-27 09:54:03.585	[aseo]
589	194	DeletePicto	Español	PUNCTUAL	verduras	2023-04-05 11:33:56.593	[Comer]

Table 7. Updated pictogram entry examples.

Index	User	Event	Language	Mode	New Name	New Voice	Old Name	Old Voice	Timestamp	Category
21	11	Update Picto	Español	PUNCTUAL	jugo de manzana	jugo de manzana	zumo de manzana	zumo de manzana	2023-05-02 18:46:14.239	[quiero beber]
145	189	Update Picto	Español	PUNCTUAL	Piano	tocando el Piano	Piano	Piano	2023-02-16 18:55:42.075	[Jugar]
191	264	Update Picto	Español	PUNCTUAL	papas fritas	papas fritas	patatas fritas	patatas fritas	2023-02-06 10:44:12.679	[Comer, De picar]

3.4. Implementation

As introduced in Section 2, once the Android app was published, it was necessary to implement a system for data collection and processing.

3.4.1. Data Collection

The data collection takes advantage of the native implementation of the connection between Android applications and the Google Firebase real-time database (available at <https://firebase.google.com/docs/database>, 24 June 2024). The app packs the data into messages in JSON format and sends them to the database identified by the “app set id” provided by Android (available at <https://developer.android.com/training/articles/app-set-id>, 24 June 2024). This ensures the original user’s privacy without compromising the data’s traceability.

3.4.2. Data Processing

It is necessary to develop a program that downloads the data from the database and converts them to a table format for further analysis. Firebase Admin SDK for Python (available at https://firebase.google.com/docs/reference/admin/python/firebase_admin, 24 June 2024) offers the functionalities of authorization and access to the database. Once the data are downloaded in dictionaries, they are formatted as tables using Pandas Python library (available at <https://pandas.pydata.org/>, 24 June 2024).

After an initial observation of the data, we define a group of general categories that include generated sentences and pictograms created based on their meanings.

- Care: Pictures and sentences that refer to personal care (hygiene, rest, affection, or clothing), such as “*Lavar las manos*” (wash hands) or “*Ir al baño*” (go to the toilet).
- Emotions: Pictures and messages relative to the user’s emotions or physical state, such as “*Yo estoy triste*” (I am sad) or “*Yo estoy cansado*” (I am tired).
- Social interaction: Pictures and utterances that help the user to perform basic daily interactions (greetings, interjections, questions, explanations, etc.), such as “*¡Hola amigos!*” (Hi friends!) or “*Ir a casa*” (go home).
- Nutrition: Pictures and messages relative to food and beverages such as “*Quiero comer*” (I want to eat) or “*Quiero agua*” (I want water).
- Leisure: Pictures and sentences involved in leisure and learning activities (board games, electronic devices, playtime, etc.), such as “*Ir al parque*” (go to the park) or “*Quiero dibujar*” (I want to draw).
- Health: Pictures and sentences that express health issues, such as “*Me duele el brazo*” (My arm hurts) or “*Dolor de cabeza*” (headache).
- Name: Only for new pictograms, including all personal names registered by users.

Additionally, we considered “incoherent” those sentences or pictograms that cannot be assigned to a single category (e.g., “*Quiero comer quiero jugar*”, I want to eat I want to play) or misspelled words (e.g., “*www*”). A group of researchers manually labeled all the samples. The labeling process was later automated, taking advantage of the fact that many samples were repetitions of the same text.

The final distribution of samples by category is represented in Table 8.

Social interactions consistently concentrate a greater number of actions, either the formation of sentences or any other events linked to the administration of pictograms. It is interesting to note that all categories are consistent in their prevalence across the different events (sentences and new, deleted, or updated pictograms).

Table 8. Sample count for each defined category.

Category	Sentences		New Pictograms		Deleted Pictograms		Updated Pictograms	
Social interaction	20,394	28.20%	650	31.01%	359	18.68%	186	31.26%
Nutrition	20,340	28.13%	686	32.73%	797	41.47%	155	26.05%
Leisure	14,038	19.41%	419	19.99%	392	20.40%	140	23.53%
Care	9273	12.82%	110	5.25%	182	9.47%	47	7.90%
Emotions	4513	6.24%	61	2.91%	134	6.97%	22	3.70%
Health	2861	3.96%	31	1.48%	26	1.35%	18	3.03%
Incoherent	889	1.23%	23	1.10%	22	1.14%	21	3.53%
Names	-	-	116	5.53%	10	0.52%	6	1.01%

3.4.3. Exploratory Analysis

Having defined the categories, we propose a set of tests to perform an exploratory analysis. These tests study the frequencies of use and the complexity of the interactions and other routine habits that represent a relevant source of knowledge for future developments in this field.

We decided to study the events of sentence generation and pictogram creation, since these are the events that provide the greatest degree of new information about the use of the app and the needs of the users. All these tests were performed using the Pandas Python library (available at <https://pandas.pydata.org/>, 24 June 2024) for data processing and the Matplotlib Python library (available at <https://matplotlib.org/>, 24 June 2024) and Seaborn python library (available at <https://seaborn.pydata.org/>, 24 June 2024) for data representation.

For the SA, we tried two different approaches. The first approach involved using a basic lexicon-based approach such as the spaCy TextBlob Python library (available at <https://spacy.io/universe/project/spacy-textblob>, 24 June 2024) and the text2emotion Python library (available at <https://pypi.org/project/text2emotion/>, 24 June 2024). The second approach involved using a more complex Large Language Model (LLM) such as Llama 3 (available at <https://llama.meta.com/llama3/>, 24 June 2024) developed by META. We chose the Ollama Python library (available at <https://ollama.com/>, 24 June 2024) to run and interact with the LLM.

When testing the text2emotion Python library on generated phrases, we determined that only 6.23% of the phrases were non-neutral, presenting several inconsistencies considering neutral phrases like “*Yo estoy contento*” (I am happy) or “*Yo estoy enfadado*” (I am angry). On the other hand, the LLM method offered more reasonable results, with 60.62% of phrases identified as non-neutral and a reduced number of inconsistencies.

Considering both approaches, we decided to discard the lexicon-based technique as it offered inadequate results, failed to provide answers for basic sentences, and had inconsistent categories for similar phrases.

4. Results and Discussion

In this section, we discuss the results of the different tests proposed for this research. We divided these tests according to the type of events they study, namely phrase generation or new pictograms. All the tests include an explanation of their goal and the insights obtained from them.

4.1. Generation Events

We seek to evaluate fundamental aspects such as the average length, the time of day, or the frequency of repetition of sentences to observe users’ behavior and needs regarding the PictoDroid Lite application. To provide more context, first, we studied user habits in terms of average number of sentences generated per day and how they distribute them throughout the day. Figure 5 presents a distribution of the users of the application regarding the average number of hours they use the application and the average number of phrases

they generate daily. On the other hand, Figure 6 presents the total number of phrases generated by each group of users defined in Figure 5. As an example, in Figure 5, there are 1295 users who generate 1 to 10 phrases daily within 0 to 1 h of use. In Figure 6, we can see that those 1295 users generated 9506 phrases.

		Average hours per day.						
		0 to 1	1 to 2	2 to 3	3 to 4	4 to 5	+5	
Average generations per day.	+50-	6	3	2	1	2	9	23 (1.23%)
	41 to 50-	10	2	1	0	1	5	19 (1.01%)
	31 to 40-	16	11	3	3	1	5	39 (2.08%)
	21 to 30-	40	10	9	0	3	13	75 (4.0%)
	11 to 20-	184	30	20	14	10	8	266 (14.19%)
	1 to 10-	1295	65	51	12	14	16	1453 (77.49%)
		1551 (82.72%)	121 (6.45%)	86 (4.59%)	30 (1.6%)	31 (1.65%)	56 (2.99%)	Users

Figure 5. Distribution of users in terms of average number of generations and usage hour span.

		Average hours per day.						
		0 to 1	1 to 2	2 to 3	3 to 4	4 to 5	+5	
Average generations per day.	+50-	689	4102	794	164	4757	14066	24572 (33.98%)
	41 to 50-	726	913	43	0	50	367	2099 (2.9%)
	31 to 40-	2011	2498	1757	103	127	319	6815 (9.42%)
	21 to 30-	2068	1463	953	0	345	3487	8316 (11.5%)
	11 to 20-	6445	2205	1571	2748	1328	930	15227 (21.06%)
	1 to 10-	9506	2752	2065	666	151	139	15279 (21.13%)
		21445 (29.66%)	13933 (19.27%)	7183 (9.93%)	3681 (5.09%)	6758 (9.35%)	19308 (26.7%)	Sent.

Figure 6. Distribution of sentences per average number of generations and usage hour span.

Figure 5 reveals that 77.49% of users generate 1 to 10 sentences in one day. Nonetheless, Figure 6 shows that only 21.13% of the sentences were generated by those users. On the other hand, 33.98% of sentences correspond to users who generate 50 or more per day. In terms of usage time, 29.66% of the sentences were generated by users who use the app one hour daily or less, while 26.70% were generated by users who use it five hours or more daily.

With this information, we can see that the majority of the users of the application generate, on average, just a few sentences in one day, but, in contrast, there are users who generate a lot of events each day. The even distribution according to the hour span indicates the existence of a smaller group of people who use the app intensively throughout the day, while a larger group uses it sporadically or for particular contexts (e.g., school, therapy, etc.). Both clues highlight how AAC communicators help users with very different needs and characteristics.

For a better understanding of this research, it is crucial to observe how frequently the users accessed the application, as many of them did not use the application during the complete data capture period. Table 9 presents the distribution of samples according to the frequency of access of the users that generated them.

Table 9. Distribution of users and samples by access frequency.

Frequency	Users	Phrases	New Pictograms
Daily	6.67%	4.64%	9.54%
Weekly	10.99%	44.65%	28.72%
Monthly	82.35%	50.71%	60.54%

A proportion of 6.67% of users generate a phrase at least once a day; almost double, the 10.99%, generate a phrase at least once a week, and the remaining 82.35% generate a phrase at least once a month. Daily and weekly generations are associated with people who use the app as an everyday tool for communication. On the other hand, monthly uses may correspond to context-specific cases (e.g., therapy or health care) or sporadic needs. The majority of both phrases and new pictograms are associated with users who use the app less than once a week. However, daily and weekly users represent half of the generated phrases and more than a third of the new pictograms.

4.1.1. What Is the Average Length of Generated Sentences for Each Category?

This analysis studies the characteristic complexity of interactions according to their meanings. Table 10 shows the number of sentences generated with the application according to their category and their average lengths in characters. We obtained the average length of the **phrase** field from Table 4.

Table 10. Test 1: Sentences in categories and their average lengths.

Category	Samples	Average Length
Social interaction	20,394	11.552
Nutrition	20,340	25.675
Leisure	14,038	17.811
Care	9273	19.083
Emotions	4513	13.293
Health	2861	13.852

Users tend to build longer sentences to communicate needs related to nutrition or care, where specificity prevails (e.g., “*Quiero comer para desayunar galletas de chocolate*”, I want to have chocolate cookies for breakfast). On the contrary, when interacting socially, they prefer to have shorter and more direct sentences (e.g., “*Hola*”, Hello, or “*Adiós*”, Good bye).

4.1.2. How Are Interactions Distributed throughout the Day?

We defined the day time slots in blocks of three hours, from midnight (00:00 to 02:59) to night (21:00 to 23:59). The **timestamp** field (see Table 4) captures time of day at which the interactions take place in local time; we can study how they are distributed over said time slots. Table 11 displays the overall distribution of interactions, and Table 12 shows how each category is distributed throughout the day.

Overall results show that users make the greatest use of the application in the mid-morning (09:00 to 11:59) and evening (18:00 to 20:59) slots.

This time distribution is coherent with time for activities (mid-morning) such as school, work, or therapy and social time at home (evening). It is relevant that the evening slot is the one with the most communicative activity.

Regarding the categories, we observe that emotions shift their interactions from the bands of greatest activity, with a very representative block in the afternoon (15:00 to 17:59). In the case of nutrition, care, and health, these are more distributed throughout the day. It is also important to point out that a significant percentage of social interaction, which more than doubles mid-morning activity and leisure, takes place in the evening slot, when most educational, occupational, and health activities take place, presumably with partners.

A plausible hypothesis that deserves further research is that for the users of these accessible tools, family is still the main source of social interaction despite inclusion efforts. It is also interesting that conversations on emotions are equally prevalent in mid-morning and evening. Usage during night hours results as expected, with few interactions mainly associated with well-being categories.

Table 11. Test 2: Percentage of usage in different time periods.

Day Slot	Hours	Samples
Midnight	00:00 to 02:59	1.75%
Dawn	03:00 to 05:59	0.55%
Morning	06:00 to 08:59	5.04%
Mid-morning	09:00 to 11:59	21.16%
Noon	12:00 to 14:59	17.37%
Afternoon	15:00 to 17:59	18.08%
Evening	18:00 to 20:59	25.89%
Night	21:00 to 23:59	10.17%

Table 12. Test 2: Usage of categories in different time periods.

Day Slot	Social Interaction	Nutrition	Leisure	Care	Emotions	Health
Midnight	0.51%	1.69%	1.45%	1.85%	3.11%	1.62%
Dawn	0.20%	0.77%	0.43%	0.49%	1.29%	0.55%
Morning	1.61%	5.64%	6.72%	4.01%	3.32%	2.99%
Mid-morning	18.30%	18.53%	21.69%	22.52%	17.58%	18.99%
Noon	10.30%	17.63%	15.09%	19.71%	17.76%	19.37%
Afternoon	11.01%	21.37%	15.20%	18.94%	26.25%	20.08%
Evening	52.12%	23.50%	30.82%	21.26%	19.33%	24.22%
Night	5.95%	10.87%	8.58%	11.23%	11.36%	12.19%

4.1.3. How Are Interactions Distributed throughout the Week?

Another relevant aspect of user habits regarding time refers to the distribution of their interactions throughout the week. Table 13 presents the global distribution of interactions. Table 14 shows the distribution of interactions depending on the category they belong to.

Table 13. Test 3: Percentage of usage on different weekdays.

Day	Total
Monday	14.76%
Tuesday	13.40%
Wednesday	18.18%
Thursday	21.69%
Friday	12.25%
Saturday	11.48%
Sunday	8.24%

Table 14. Test 3: Usage of categories on different weekdays.

Day	Social Interaction	Nutrition	Leisure	Care	Emotions	Health
Monday	20.69%	10.57%	15.52%	12.00%	12.52%	11.15%
Tuesday	10.36%	14.03%	13.90%	14.08%	15.67%	22.23%
Wednesday	23.26%	16.36%	15.36%	17.20%	16.53%	14.58%
Thursday	26.46%	18.30%	21.61%	20.16%	21.76%	17.02%
Friday	9.16%	13.25%	13.79%	13.68%	13.52%	13.00%
Saturday	5.82%	15.35%	11.87%	14.49%	11.26%	12.90%
Sunday	4.26%	12.13%	7.96%	8.38%	8.75%	9.12%

The general distribution shows that usage through the week is rather evenly distributed, peaking in the middle of the week and declining on Sundays. Category-wise, we observe that nutrition has the most consistent distribution over the week, while categories like social interaction, emotions, and leisure are mostly reserved for working days, when users may attend to school, their workplace, or therapy sessions.

4.1.4. What Is the Frequency of Sentence Repetition in Small Time Slots?

Data represent the characteristic behavior of certain users, tending to repeat sentences consecutively with a short time margin between them. This behavior might be a signal of urgency or necessity, or it might be a call for attention.

To study this phenomenon, we defined two different time margins in order to consider when one sentence is reiterated under 3 s and under 5 s. We calculated the time differences between the **timestamp** fields of consecutive iterations. Table 15 shows the percentage of sentences that were considered repetitions for each category.

Table 15. Test 4: Percentage of repetitions of sentences.

Category	Samples	3 s Reiteration	5 s Reiteration
Social interaction	20,394	11.03%	13.73%
Nutrition	20,340	15.08%	16.05%
Leisure	14,038	10.03%	12.10%
Care	9273	23.66%	34.45%
Emotions	4513	19.79%	21.58%
Health	2861	20.90%	23.31%

We observe a greater incidence for categories associated with personal well-being and care and health, accounting for 34% and 23% of repetitions in less than 5 s, respectively.

4.2. New Pictogram Events

Studying the general habits of users while registering new pictograms, we observed the distribution of image sources for the creation of pictograms with the **source** field (see Table 5). We could see that 55.87% of the pictograms were downloaded from the ARASAAC repository, 37.31% from the device's gallery, and the final 6.82% directly captured

from the app. This indicates that users find it valuable to have an accessible source of standardized pictograms.

Another relevant behavior refers to how commonly pictograms of an equal category are created simultaneously. Table 16 shows the proportion of pictograms belonging to each category, which were created along with pictograms in the same category.

Table 16. Percentage of equal-category pictograms created together.

Category	Samples
Social interaction	56.90%
Nutrition	59.91%
Care	27.94%
Leisure	48.55%
Emotions	54.17%
Health	29.41%
Names	53.66%

These results suggest that for categories like nutrition or social interaction, users tend to create most of the pictograms they need at the same time, while for categories like care or health, they prefer to add new pictograms when they need them.

4.2.1. What Is the Indexing Level of Newly Created Pictograms Depending on Their Category?

Punctual mode offers a system of indexed pictograms. This way, “folder” pictograms can be established, serving as a container for related concepts that will be selected in the next level, adding extra precision to the sentence. We consider the level of indexation as the number of folders and subfolders in which a new pictogram is created. To illustrate this methodology, the default configuration of PictoDroid Lite contains the pictogram “apple” inside the pictogram subfolder “fruit”, which is included in the pictogram folder “eat”. This means that the pictogram “apple” presents a second level of indexation.

This analysis studies which categories show the highest degree of indexing. We know the level of indexation by observing the length of the list present in the **category** field (see Table 5). Figure 7 shows the distribution of new pictograms according to their level of indexing and the category they belong to.

Figure 7. Distribution of pictograms regarding their indexation and the category they belong to.

Results clearly show that the nutrition category is the one that benefits the most from this indexing system, reaching up to four levels and with a broad representation of alternatives in each of them. Another relevant aspect is that the social interaction category tends to host all pictograms in an unindexed format, presumably for quick, straightforward access, in comparison with categories such as emotions, names, or health, with almost anecdotal representation of unindexed pictograms. In the case of names, they are created mostly in indexed form to be used as objects in the generated sentences (“*Quiero estar con profe María*”, I want to be with teacher María).

4.2.2. What Is the Average Length of Newly Created Pictograms for Each Category?

As with the generated sentences, by studying the average length of the **name** of the pictograms created for each category (see Table 5), we can deduce the complexity of the communication. Table 17 shows the average length, in characters, of the written texts of the created pictograms.

Table 17. Test 6: Average length of new pictograms in the different categories.

Category	Samples	Length
Social interaction	650	6.378
Nutrition	686	9.370
Leisure	419	8.795
Care	110	7.745
Emotions	61	7.639
Health	31	8.903
Names	116	5.405

Categories such as health, nutrition, and leisure opt for longer constructions (e.g., “*Dolor de garganta*”, sore throat), while categories like care and social interaction prefer more direct expressions (e.g., “*Dormir*”, sleep, or “*Hola*”, hello). It is noticeable that compared with the results obtained in Test 1 (see Section 4.1.1), there is not much difference in the average length of the sentences and the pictograms alone for categories like health, emotions, and social interaction (less than double the length). We see the opposite situation for categories such as care and nutrition, where the average length of sentences triples the length of their pictograms. This seems to back up the interpretation that categories such as health or social interaction prioritize immediacy, while nutrition and care communications prioritize specificity.

4.3. Sentiment Analysis

With a general perspective on data, we considered it necessary to perform an analysis of the prevalence of the most relevant emotions (happiness, sadness, fear, and anger) in the communications captured with the application. With this analysis, we can understand not only the way users communicate thanks to the application but also their main motivations for doing so. Table 18 shows the percentage of phrases that present any of the emotions previously listed for each category. We added a neutral column for those where no particular emotion stands out.

Table 18. Sentiment analysis of generation events.

Category	Happiness	Anger	Sadness	Fear	Neutral
Social interaction	46.46%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	53.53%
Nutrition	97.82%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	2.18%
Leisure	78.83%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	21.17%
Care	6.30%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	93.70%
Emotions	42.10%	2.57%	28.87%	0.60%	25.86%
Health	0.00%	0.00%	73.19%	0.00%	26.81%

For categories such as nutrition and leisure, we observe that an overwhelming majority of the interactions have an inherently positive emotion, as they mostly express desires for food or recreation. As expected, the emotions category presents the most wide range of emotions, being the only one where anger is expressed. Finally, health stands out, as the majority of entries express sadness, which is logical, given the fact that most the associated clauses are used to express discomfort. For care and social interaction, the majority of sentences are neutral.

We also considered conducting this analysis on newly added pictograms despite the limitation of the length of the added terms. Table 19 presents the results of this analysis.

Table 19. Sentiment analysis of new pictograms.

Category	Happiness	Anger	Sadness	Fear	Neutral
Social interaction	18.92%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	81.08%
Nutrition	37.46%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	62.54%
Leisure	27.68%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	72.32%
Care	10.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	90.00%
Emotions	34.43%	18.03%	14.75%	4.92%	27.87%
Health	0.00%	12.90%	0.00%	0.00%	87.10%

As the new pictograms are fractions of phrases, most of them lack complete meaning by themselves. This is why the majority are classified as neutral in all categories except emotions. We considered it interesting that the pictograms created under the latter are as evenly distributed as the generation events for the same category. In particular, the difference between the creation of new pictograms that represent anger and their use could mean that users identify a lack of predefined terms to express this emotion.

5. Conclusions

This research studies the usage habits of an AAC application, seeking a better understanding of the needs of its target users. This information is particularly useful in achieving better adaptation of AAC strategies to those needs. Adaptation is key for smarter, easier, and more efficient use, enabling more fluent interactions. An analysis of the state of the art revealed the singularity of the perspective of this research, prioritizing usage patterns over more clinic aspects of AAC and benefiting from a larger group of participants.

The data retrieved with PictoDroid Lite demonstrates that it is a useful tool reaching target users who demand accessible solutions, even from LMICs. Additionally, being distributed a platform as large as the Android operating system, applications such as PictoDroid Lite can offer their potential and services without cost restrictions or dedicated hardware specifications.

The tests conducted in this research revealed meaningful insights with respect to common usage of AAC applications. Our observations regarding the complexity of the generated phrases suggest that many users could benefit from using more complex methods like the cumulative mode, which offers greater versatility when building said sentences. Nevertheless, the immediacy and straightforwardness of the punctual mode have been proven useful and, by far, more appealing to the general public.

Furthermore, the conclusions drawn from the SA reinforce the idea that AAC communicators need to include default resources to express emotions besides the most functional or routine expressions. AAC users demand ways to express how they are feeling, including positive and negative emotions.

Limitations and Future Improvements

The tests and analysis performed in this study offer a privileged window into the everyday life of the people who need accessible communications. By this means and with due respect to privacy, we were allowed to observe their main concerns, how they adapt the application to their needs, and what their communication patterns are. From the test

observations, we identified a series of limitations present in PictoDroid Lite (and many other communicators) and investigated how those limitations could be solved for any AAC application.

- **Specific profiles:** Observing the newly created pictograms and usage patterns, we conclude that the application could be offered alongside a set of predefined profiles adapted to specific contexts, such as school, health care, or playgrounds. This would reduce the time needed to navigate the pictogram grid and would make personalization faster and smarter.
- **Pictogram suggestion:** When creating a new pictogram on a predefined profile or when doing so in a given category, the application could suggest related concepts in order to make the creation process more dynamic.
- **Time-based sorting.** Test 2 (see Section 4.1.2) highlighted that users have different needs at different times of the day. The application could adapt to these changes by rearranging the grid, giving priority to those categories that are more likely to be needed at a particular time of the day. Test 3 (see Section 4.1.4) indicates that this could be useful for weekday adaption.
- **Repeat last action:** Test 4 (see Section 4.2.1) showed that users tend to repeat the same sentence one or many times. This process could be helped by introducing a button that allows one to repeat the last sentence without needing to navigate the grid again. This would be notably useful in urgent contexts.

Observing the applications cited in Table 1, almost all of them lack some or every point cited above. Apps like Card Talk, SymboTalk, and Twinkl Symbols include mechanics for category distinction, like communication boards. However, these boards do not constitute an entity similar to having a domain-specific profile, as our clues suggest.

On the edition and creation of new symbols, no application includes suggestions based on related concepts. The applications that include an online search of pictograms (ARASAAC being the most frequent source) only recommend other pictograms that also include the search query.

Regarding user experience, no application has previously considered time (time of the day, day of the week, etc.) as a relevant factor for adaption. Additionally, those applications that seek to provide fluent support for communication could consider introducing a shortcut for last-phrase reiteration.

We detected a set of strengths already implemented in PictoDroid Lite that would be positive for other existing applications. The method of pictogram indexation provides a straightforward method for sentence construction, SymboTalk being the only studied application that includes a similar technique. Moreover, developers should consider including access to an online source of predefined pictograms such as ARASAAC, as 55.87% of users find it useful.

The performed analysis led to relevant clues about the development of AAC mobile applications, highlighting the strengths of some methodologies implemented in PictoDroid Lite and noting some gaps that many applications present. These areas of improvement, if fixed, would result in more efficient communication and offer better service to AAC users. In other words, this research shows that communicators (and other AAC applications) like PictoDroid Lite have a margin for automated responsiveness that would serve the needs and preferences of most users well.

Author Contributions: J.G.-G.: Methodology, software, validation, formal analysis, investigation, data curation, and writing—original draft. E.C.-M.: conceptualization, methodology, investigation, formal analysis, writing—review and editing, and supervision. F.M.G.-D.: conceptualization, methodology, investigation, formal analysis, writing—review and editing, and supervision. C.L.-B.: methodology, formal analysis, writing—review and editing, and supervision. F.d.A.-P.: software, formal analysis, writing—review and editing, and supervision. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This work was partially supported by (i) Xunta de Galicia grant ED481A-2023-090, Spain; (ii) Xunta de Galicia grant ED481B-2022-093, Spain; (iii) Xunta de Galicia grant ED431C 2022/04, Spain; (iv) Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación grant TED2021-130824B-C21, Spain; and (v) University of Vigo/CISUG for partial open access charge.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The raw data supporting the conclusions of this article will be made available by the authors upon request.

Acknowledgments: The pictographic symbols used in this paper are the property of the Government of Aragón and were created by Sergio Palao for ARASAAC (<http://www.arasaac.org>, accessed on 24 June 2024), which distributes them under Creative Commons License BY-NC-SA. We wish to thank Jonathan Juncal Martínez and José María López Astáriz for their contribution in the development of the application.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

AAC	Augmentative and Alternative Communication
NLG	Natural Language Generation
LLM	Large Language Model
LMIC	Low and Middle-Income Country
SDK	Software Development Kit

References

1. Calculator, S. Roles and responsibilities of speech-language pathologists with respect to augmentative and alternative communication: Technical report. *ASHA Suppl.* **2004**, *17*, 48–59
2. Farzana, W.; Sarker, F.; Chau, T.; Mamun, K.A. Technological Evolvement in AAC Modalities to Foster Communications of Verbally Challenged ASD Children: A Systematic Review. *IEEE Access* **2021**, 2169–3536. [[CrossRef](#)]
3. Logan, K.; Iacono, T.; Trembath, D. A systematic review of research into aided AAC to increase social-communication functions in children with autism spectrum disorder. *AAC Augment. Altern. Commun.* **2017**, *33*, 1267795. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
4. Bautista, S.; Hervás, R.; Hernández-Gil, A.; Martínez-Díaz, C.; Pascua, S.; Gervás, P. Ara traductor: Text to pictogram translation using natural language processing techniques. In Proceedings of the XVIII International Conference on Human Computer Interaction, Cancun, Mexico, 25–27 September 2017; Volume Part F131194, pp. 1–8. [[CrossRef](#)]
5. Collette, D.; Brix, A.; Brennan, P.; DeRoma, N.; Muir, B.C. Proloquo2Go Enhances Classroom Performance in Children With Autism Spectrum Disorder. *OTJR Occup. Particip. Health* **2019**, *39*, 143–150. [[CrossRef](#)]
6. Hervás, R.; Bautista, S.; Méndez, G.; Galván, P.; Gervás, P. Predictive composition of pictogram messages for users with autism. *J. Ambient. Intell. Humaniz. Comput.* **2020**, *11*, 5649–5664. [[CrossRef](#)]
7. Beukelman, D.R.; Mirenda, P. *Augmentative & Alternative Communication. Supporting Children and Adults with Complex Communication Needs*; Paul Brookes Publishing Co.: Baltimore, MD, USA, 2005.
8. Dietz, A.; Wallace, S.E.; Weissling, K. Revisiting the role of augmentative and alternative communication in aphasia rehabilitation. *Am. J. Speech-Lang. Pathol.* **2020**, *29*, 909–913. [[CrossRef](#)]
9. Fager, S.K.; Burnfield, J.M.; Pfeifer, C.M.; Sorenson, T. Perceived importance of AAC messages to support communication in rehabilitation settings. *Disabil. Rehabil. Assist. Technol.* **2021**, *16*, 1736652. [[CrossRef](#)]
10. Babb, S.; Jung, S.; Ousley, C.; McNaughton, D.; Light, J. Personalized AAC Intervention to Increase Participation and Communication for a Young Adult with down Syndrome. *Top. Lang. Disord.* **2021**, *41*, 232–248. [[CrossRef](#)]
11. Moorcroft, A.; Scarinci, N.; Meyer, C. A systematic review of the barriers and facilitators to the provision and use of low-tech and unaided AAC systems for people with complex communication needs and their families. *Disabil. Rehabil. Assist. Technol.* **2019**, *14*, 1499135. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
12. Roche, L.; Sigafoos, J.; Trembath, D. Augmentative and Alternative Communication Intervention for People With Angelman Syndrome: A Systematic Review. *Curr. Dev. Disord. Rep.* **2020**, *7*, 28–34. [[CrossRef](#)]
13. Carbone, V.J.; Sweeney-Kerwin, E.J.; Attanasio, V.; Kasper, T. Increasing the vocal responses of children with autism and developmental disabilities using manual sign mand training and prompt delay. *J. Appl. Behav. Anal.* **2010**, *43*, 705–709. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

14. Calculator, S.N. Use of enhanced natural gestures to foster interactions between children with Angelman syndrome and their parents. *Am. J. Speech-Lang. Pathol.* **2002**, *11*, 340–355. [[CrossRef](#)]
15. Biggs, E.E.; Carter, E.W.; Gilson, C.B. A scoping review of the involvement of children’s communication partners in aided augmentative and alternative communication modeling interventions. *Am. J. Speech-Lang. Pathol.* **2019**, *28*, 743–758. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
16. Bondy, A.S.; Frost, L.A. The Picture Exchange Communication System. *Focus Autism Other Dev. Disabil.* **1994**, *9*, 1–19. [[CrossRef](#)]
17. Balandin, S.; Hemsley, B.; Sigafoos, J.; Green, V.; Forbes, R.; Taylor, C.; Parmenter, T. Communicating with Nurses: The Experiences of 10 Individuals with an Acquired Severe Communication Impairment. *Brain Impair.* **2001**, *2*, 109–118. [[CrossRef](#)]
18. Balandin, S.; Hemsley, B.; Sigafoos, J.; Green, V. Communicating with nurses: The experiences of 10 adults with cerebral palsy and complex communication needs. *Appl. Nurs. Res.* **2007**, *20*, 56–62. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
19. Morin, K.L.; Ganz, J.B.; Gregori, E.V.; Foster, M.J.; Gerow, S.L.; Genç-Tosun, D.; Hong, E.R. A systematic quality review of high-tech AAC interventions as an evidence-based practice. *AAC Augment. Altern. Commun.* **2018**, *34*, 104–117. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
20. Voon, N.H.; Bazilah, S.N.; Maidin, A.; Jumaat, H.; Ahmad, M.Z. Autisay: A mobile communication tool for autistic individuals. In Proceedings of the Computational Intelligence in Information Systems, Burgos, Spain, 15–17 June 2015; Volume 331, pp. 349–359. [[CrossRef](#)]
21. Zaffke, A.; Jain, N.; Johnson, N.; Alam, M.A.U.; Magiera, M.; Ahamed, S.I. Icanlearn: A mobile application for creating flashcards and social stories™ for children with autism. In Proceedings of the Smart Homes and Health Telematics, Geneva, Switzerland, 10–12 June 2015; Volume 8456, pp. 225–230. [[CrossRef](#)]
22. Mohammad, H.; Abu-Amara, F. A mobile social and communication tool for autism. *Int. J. Emerg. Technol. Learn.* **2019**, *14*, 159–167. [[CrossRef](#)]
23. Sng, C.Y.; Carter, M.; Stephenson, J. Teaching on-Topic Conversational Responses to Students with Autism Spectrum Disorders Using an iPad App. *Int. J. Disabil. Dev. Educ.* **2022**, *69*, 415–434. [[CrossRef](#)]
24. Sennott, S.C.; Akagi, L.; Lee, M.; Rhodes, A. AAC and Artificial Intelligence (AI). *Top. Lang. Disord.* **2019**, *39*, 389–403. [[CrossRef](#)]
25. Liu, R.; Salisbury, J.P.; Vahabzadeh, A.; Sahin, N.T. Feasibility of an autism-focused augmented reality smartglasses system for social communication and behavioral coaching. *Front. Pediatr.* **2017**, *5*, 145. [[CrossRef](#)]
26. Elshahar, Y.; Hu, S.; Bouazza-Marouf, K.; Kerr, D.; Mansor, A. Augmentative and alternative communication (AAC) advances: A review of configurations for individuals with a speech disability. *Sensors* **2019**, *19*, 1911. [[CrossRef](#)]
27. Kar, A.; Corcoran, P. A review and analysis of eye-gaze estimation systems, algorithms and performance evaluation methods in consumer platforms. *IEEE Access* **2017**, *5*, 16495–16519. [[CrossRef](#)]
28. Chen, S.H.K.; O’Leary, M. Eye Gaze 101: What Speech-Language Pathologists Should Know About Selecting Eye Gaze Augmentative and Alternative Communication Systems. *Perspect. ASHA Spec. Interest Groups* **2018**, *3*, 24–32. [[CrossRef](#)]
29. Ozioko, O.; Dahiya, R. Smart Tactile Gloves for Haptic Interaction, Communication, and Rehabilitation. *Adv. Intell. Syst.* **2022**, *4*, 2100091. [[CrossRef](#)]
30. Gonçalves, C.W.P.; Richa, R.A.; Bo, A.P. Tracking and Classification of Head Movement for Augmentative and Alternative Communication Systems. *Sensors* **2022**, *22*, 435. [[CrossRef](#)]
31. Elshahar, Y.; Bouazza-Marouf, K.; Kerr, D.; Gaur, A.; Kaushik, V.; Hu, S. Breathing pattern interpretation as an alternative and effective voice communication solution. *Biosensors* **2018**, *8*, 48. [[CrossRef](#)]
32. Brumberg, J.S.; Pitt, K.M.; Mantie-Kozlowski, A.; Burnison, J.D. Brain—Computer interfaces for augmentative and alternative communication: A tutorial. *Am. J. Speech-Lang. Pathol.* **2018**, *27*, 1–12. [[CrossRef](#)]
33. Rodriguez, C.S.; Rowe, M.; Thomas, L.; Shuster, J.; Koepfel, B.; Cairns, P. Enhancing the communication of suddenly speechless critical care patients. *Am. J. Crit. Care* **2016**, *25*, e40–e47. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
34. Agius, M.M.; Vance, M. A Comparison of PECS and iPad to Teach Requesting to Pre-schoolers with Autistic Spectrum Disorders. *AAC Augment. Altern. Commun.* **2016**, *32*, 58–68. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
35. Broomfield, K.; Harrop, D.; Jones, G.L.; Sage, K.; Judge, S. A qualitative evidence synthesis of the experiences and perspectives of communicating using augmentative and alternative communication (AAC). *Disabil. Rehabil. Assist. Technol.* **2022**, *2022*, 2105961. [[CrossRef](#)]
36. García-Méndez, S.; Fernández-Gavilanes, M.; Costa-Montenegro, E.; Juncal-Martínez, J.; González-Castaño, F.J. A library for automatic natural language generation of Spanish texts. *Expert Syst. Appl.* **2019**, *120*, 372–386. [[CrossRef](#)]
37. Caron, J.; Light, J.; Drager, K. Operational Demands of AAC Mobile Technology Applications on Programming Vocabulary and Engagement during Professional and Child Interactions. *AAC Augment. Altern. Commun.* **2016**, *32*, 12–24. [[CrossRef](#)]
38. Muttiah, N.; Gormley, J.; Drager, K.D. A scoping review of Augmentative and Alternative Communication (AAC) interventions in Low-and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs). *AAC Augment. Altern. Commun.* **2022**, *38*, 123–134. [[CrossRef](#)]

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